

Synthesis and Ion-exchange Characteristics of Thermally Stable Tin(IV) Molybdophosphate. Separation of Mercury(II) from Lead(II) and Thorium(IV)

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A new thermally stable inorganic ion-exchange material, tin(IV) molybdophosphate has been synthesised, characterised, K_d values for 16 metal ions in demineralised water and in different solutions have been determined on various phases and successful separations of Hg^{II} from Pb^{II} and Th^{IV} have been achieved.

HETEROPOLYACID salts of some polyvalent metal ions have been used as inorganic ion-exchangers. Qureshi *et al.* have published their findings on tungstoarsenate^{1,2}, vanadophosphate³, molybdoarsenate⁴, vanadotungstate⁵, molybdosilicate⁶ and tungstophosphate⁷ of tin(IV). This report describes the synthesis and ion-exchange behaviour of thermally stable tin(IV) molybdophosphate.

Experimental

Stannic chloride pentahydrate (Baker), sodium molybdate dihydrate (veb Jenapharm) and sodium orthophosphate (AnalaR) were used. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

A Elico L-19T pH meter for pH titration measurements, Spekol Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer for colorimetric determinations, a Spectromom-2000 for IR spectra, a muffle furnace for heat treatment and a thermobalance for thermogravimetric analysis were used.

Synthesis of tin(IV) molybdophosphates: The sample of tin(IV) molybdophosphate were prepared by mixing acidic solutions of 0.1 M stannic chloride, 0.1 M sodium molybdate and 0.1 M sodium orthophosphate in a volume ratio 2 : 1 : 1 at different pH values, but the product obtained at pH 1.0 was chosen for detailed studies on account of its better mechanical stability. Elemental composition of the product was found to be (in ratio) Sn, 1.0 ; Mo, 0.33 ; P, 2.0.

pH-titrations were performed using glass and saturated calomel electrodes. IR spectra of the sample in the H⁺-form dried at 50° were recorded using KBr disc technique. Tin(IV) molybdophosphate sample was heated in a muffle furnace at a different temperatures for 1 h. The thermogram was

recorded at heating rate of 10°/min under the atmosphere of N₂.

K_d values for 16 metal ions were determined in demineralised water, HNO₃, NH₄NO₃ and in the mixture of HNO₃ and NH₄NO₃ solutions. These values in demineralised water were also determined on the phases dried at 200, 400 and 600°. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1— K_d VALUES (ml g⁻¹) OF METAL IONS ON TIN(IV) MOLYBDOPHOSPHATE DRIED AT 50° IN DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS

Cation	0.01N HNO ₃	0.1N HNO ₃	0.1M NH ₄ NO ₃	1M NH ₄ NO ₃	0.1M MH ₄ NO ₃ + 0.1M HNO ₃ (1 : 1)
Mg ^{II}	28	4	0	0	0
Ca ^{II}	100	50	8	53	14
Si ^{II}	29	20	23	92	67
Ba ^{II}	212	56	38	38	19
Zn ^{II}	21	113	18	2	2
Cd ^{II}	200	38	30	6	4
Hg ^{II}	3	3	3	0	0
Cu ^{II}	27	60	130	6	14
Co ^{II}	0	0	20	9	0
Ni ^{II}	0	22	78	28	3
Mn ^{II}	0	8	16	2	8
Pb ^{II}	68	13	CU	CU	125
Al ^{III}	8	0	9	0	2
Fe ^{III}	110	37	48	11	5
Bi ^{III}	CU	550	CU	317	733
Th ^{IV}	200	28	550	308	92

CU = Complete uptake.

For separations, tin(IV) molybdophosphate (1 g) in the H⁺-form was placed in a glass column (30 × 0.3 cm) over a glass wool support. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2— K_d VALUES (ml g⁻¹) OF METAL ION ON TIN(IV) MOLYBDOPHOSPHATE DRIED AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN DEMINERALISED WATER

Cation	50°	200°	400°	600°
Mg ^{II}	200	127	265	242
Ca ^{II}	287	127	257	218
Sr ^{II}	966	89	317	390
Ba ^{II}	400	150	733	525
Zn ^{II}	205	88	488	1 075
Cd ^{II}	425	82	291	390
Hg ^{II}	3	18	7	3
Cu ^{II}	120	67	117	320
Co ^{II}	900	38	34	70
Ni ^{II}	137	42	30	122
Mn ^{II}	550	29	210	433
Pb ^{II}	1 020	625	CU	CU
Al ^{III}	133	75	234	317
Fe ^{III}	284	56	133	CU
Bi ^{III}	CU	550	CU	CU
Th ^{IV}	625	25	CU	CU

CU = Complete uptake.

TABLE 3—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON TIN(IV) MOLYBDOPHOSPHATE

Mixture	Amount loaded (μg)	Amount found (μg)	% Error
Hg ^{II} - Pb ^{II}	1 000	954	-4.60
	517	538	+4.06
Hg ^{II} - Th ^{IV}	1 100	1 060	-3.64
	348	325	-6.60

Eluents for Hg^{II}, dmw : for Pb^{II}, 1M NH₄NO₃; for Th^{IV}, 0.1 M HNO₃.

Results and Discussions

The product obtained at pH 1.0 is fairly stable in 4 M H₂SO₄, 4 M HCl, 1 M HNO₃, 1 M tartaric acid and in 1 M NH₄NO₃ but it gets dissolved completely in 1 M NaOH solution. The pH titration results confirm the monofunctional behaviour of the product.

The ion-exchange capacity (meq/g) for various cations in the product is as follows: Li⁺(0.37), Na⁺(0.99), K⁺(1.40), Mg²⁺(0.66), Ca²⁺(0.68), Sr²⁺(0.79) and Ba²⁺(0.90). This trend in ion-exchange capacity confirms that the ion-exchange takes place in hydrated form.

It is found that the phases dried at different drying temperatures show different ion-exchange capacity (meq/g) for Na⁺ ions: 50° (0.99), 200° (0.52), 400° (0.44), 600° (0.23), 800° (0.00) and 1 000°

(0.00). These data confirm that the phase dried at 600° retains 25% ion-exchange capacity that of the phase dried at 50°. The thermogravimetric analysis results of tin(IV) molybdophosphate shows a 25.4% continuous weight loss from 50 to 700°, and above 700° there is no weight loss upto 1 000°.

Ir spectral data of tin(IV) molybdophosphate sample dried at 50° show peaks at 3 400, 1 600, 900, 650 and 330 cm⁻¹. The peaks at 3 400 and 1 600 cm⁻¹ correspond to the vibrations of hydroxyl groups and interstitial water. The peak at 900 cm⁻¹ is due to P-O vibration in PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻, and H PO₄⁻; peak at 650 cm⁻¹ represents metal oxygen stretching vibrations. The last peak at 330 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the interatomic stretching vibrations.

Tables 1 and 2 show the distribution coefficients on tin(IV) molybdophosphate. The selectivity sequence varies from one solution to the other. It decreases upon increasing the ionic strength with the addition of nitric acid, ammonium nitrate or both in the exchange solution. To establish its thermal stability K_d values in demineralised water have been determined on various phases dried at different temperatures. Table 2 shows the high uptake of most of the metal ions except Hg^{II}. The comparative study of Tables 1 and 2 reveals the higher preference for Pb^{II}, Bi^{III} and Th^{IV} by tin(IV) molybdophosphate while Hg^{II} is not preferred. Hence, Hg^{II} can be separated from Pb^{II}, Bi^{III} and Th^{IV}, and we have achieved the separations of Hg^{II} from Pb^{II} and Th^{IV} successfully. The results are given in Table 3.

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